

Quantifying Stochastic Geometric Effects in the HTR-PROTEUS Benchmark

Spencer C. Ercanbrack^{1,*}, Olin Calvin², Javier Ortensi², John D. Bess³, Volkan Seker⁴

¹North Carolina State University, 2500 Stinson Avenue, Raleigh, NC;

²Idaho National Laboratory, 1955 Fremont Avenue, Idaho Falls, Idaho;

³J. Foster and Associates, 425 North Capital Avenue, Idaho Falls, Idaho;

⁴University of Michigan, 2355 Bonisteel Boulevard, Ann Arbor, Michigan

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803512

ABSTRACT

This work systematically quantifies geometric uncertainty in the HTR-PROTEUS Core 4.2 benchmark to support the DOE/NRC Criticality Safety for Commercial-Scale HALEU Fuel Cycle and Transportation (DNCSH) project. Using a discrete element method-based software packaged called Chrono::GPU, 110 realistic random pebble packings were generated for Monte Carlo transport calculations using Shift, Serpent, and MCNP. These packings are more consistent with realistic packing physics than other modeling approaches. Results show that uncertainty in k_{eff} from the Chrono::GPU produced pebble positioning (~ 30 pcm) is less than half that of OpenMC-produced packings (~ 68 pcm). Analysis of TRISO particle positioning methods reveals that the legacy modeling approach of using an ordered lattice representation of TRISO particles underestimate k_{eff} by approximately 25 pcm compared to true random positioning, with semi-random methods showing 15-18 pcm differences. This work directly supports the HALEU Availability Program by providing analyses and computational methods for systems with random pebble packings and TRISO particle positions, relevant for modern pebble bed reactors and scenarios where ordered pebble arrangements cannot be guaranteed.

Keywords: Pebble Bed Reactor, Advanced Reactor, Uncertainty Quantification, HALEU, Verification and Validation

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Motivation

The development and deployment of advanced nuclear reactor technologies increasingly rely on High-Assay Low-Enriched Uranium (HALEU) fuel, defined as uranium enriched between 5% and 20% in ^{235}U . HALEU offers significant advantages over conventional low-enriched uranium (LEU) fuel used in light water reactors, including higher energy density, which enables more compact reactor designs, extended operating cycles, and improved overall system efficiency. These characteristics make HALEU particularly attractive for emerging reactor concepts, including small modular reactors (SMRs), microreactors, and Generation IV designs such as high-temperature gas-cooled reactors (HTGRs) and molten salt reactors. The integration of HALEU into the United States commercial nuclear fuel cycle presents substantial infrastructure and regulatory challenges. Current U.S. capabilities for HALEU enrichment, fabrication, transportation, and storage remain limited. Recognizing these challenges, the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) established the HALEU Availability Program (HAP) to facilitate the development of domestic HALEU supply chains and supporting infrastructure. A critical component of the HAP is the joint DOE/Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) Criticality Safety for Commercial-Scale HALEU Fuel Cycle and Transportation (DNCSH) project, which aims to establish new criticality benchmark data crucial for licensing facilities and certifying transportation packages. The DNCSH project addresses a fundamental need: reducing uncertainty in criticality safety evaluations for HALEU systems, particularly for fuel transportation and storage where reactivity control is paramount [1].

*scercanb@ncsu.edu

1.2. Background of the HTR-Proteus System and Benchmarks

The PROTEUS zero-power research reactor at the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI) in Switzerland was configured as a pebble-bed reactor critical facility from 1992 to 1996 and designated as HTR-PROTEUS. During this period, seventeen critical configurations were assembled and various reactor physics experiments were conducted. The HTR-PROTEUS experimental program was part of an International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) Coordinated Research Project (CRP) focused on validating safety-related physics calculations for low-enriched HTGRs. The facility consisted of a cylindrical graphite annulus with a central cavity loaded with various pebble configurations [2]. The fuel pebbles contained 16.76% enriched UO_2 tristructural-isotropic (TRISO) particles embedded in a graphite matrix, representing one of the few sources of high-quality experimental data for systems with TRISO-HALEU fuel, graphite moderators and reflectors, and significant neutron leakage. Core Configuration 4 is unique as the only configuration with randomly packed pebbles, particularly relevant for modern pebble bed reactor designs and accident or transportation scenarios where ordered arrangements cannot be guaranteed.

Four benchmark reports evaluating eleven critical configurations were previously prepared and included in the International Reactor Physics Experiment Evaluation Project (IRPhEP) Handbook, with Core Configuration 4 being unique as the only configuration with randomly packed pebbles. This random packing is particularly relevant for modern pebble bed reactor designs and for certain accident scenarios or transportation conditions where ordered pebble arrangements cannot be guaranteed.

Despite the high quality of the HTR-PROTEUS benchmark data, significant variability (~ 345 pcm) in computed k_{eff} has been encountered [2]. Two potential contributors to this variability are:

1. Pebble positioning uncertainty: Random packing of spherical pebbles leads to statistical variations in local geometry
2. TRISO particle positioning: The random dispersion of approximately 9,394 TRISO particles within each fuel pebble introduces another layer of stochastic behavior

Previous analyses have shown pebble positioning contributing about 45 pcm to the overall uncertainty in k_{eff} stated above [2]. The primary objective of this work is to systematically quantify and further analyze these sources of uncertainty in the HTR-PROTEUS benchmark, thereby supporting the DNCSH project by reducing modeling uncertainties and providing validated computational methods for HALEU systems relevant to transportation and storage scenarios.

Section 2 of this paper discusses the methodology used in this work, with the results and discussion presented in Section 3 and conclusions provided in Section 4.

2. METHODS

2.1. HTR-Proteus Core 4 Benchmark Description

The HTR-PROTEUS facility at the Paul Scherrer Institute consisted of the PROTEUS zero-power research reactor configured as a pebble-bed reactor critical facility. The baseline geometry comprises a cylindrical graphite annulus with a central cavity that was loaded with spherical fuel and moderator pebbles. This analysis focused specifically on the PROTEUS-GCR-EXP-002 benchmark, designated as "Core 4" in the IRPhEP Handbook, which represents random pebble packing configurations with a 1:1 moderator-to-fuel pebble ratio.

The fuel pebbles have a diameter of 6.0 cm and contain approximately 9,394 TRISO particles randomly dispersed within a graphite matrix. Each TRISO particle consists of a UO_2 kernel enriched to 16.76% in ^{235}U , surrounded by multiple protective coating layers (buffer, inner pyrolytic carbon, silicon carbide, and outer pyrolytic carbon). The moderator pebbles are solid graphite spheres of identical diameter. The pebble packing fraction in Core 4 is approximately 0.61, while the TRISO packing fraction within each fuel pebble is approximately 0.0694.

Multiple variations of Core 4 were created; designated as Cores 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3, respectively. The differences between each variation include total number of pebbles used, the active core height, and pebble loading methodology. This work describes the analysis of Core 4.2, whose key characteristics are included below in Table I. Reference [2] contains more model details.

Table I. Core 4.2 Key Characteristics.

Pebble Count	4940 Moderator, 4940 Fuel
Core Height	1.52 ± 0.01 m
Rod Positions (Control/Autorod)	160.0/47.0 cm

2.2. Computational Approach Overview

The methodology employed in this work involved multiple stages. First, the HTR-Proteus Core 4.2 was modeled using the Shift [3], Serpent [4], and MCNP [5] codes. To generate physically realistic positions for the fuel and moderator pebbles, a software package called Chrono::GPU was used. 110 random pebble packings were generated; that is, 110 unique sets of coordinates for all 9,880 pebbles were produced. A Python script sorted the coordinate sets, tagging every other one as fuel and the remainder as moderator. These coordinates were then inserted into the Shift and Serpent models, resulting in 110 unique input files for each code. The 'disperse' function of Serpent was then used to generate the set of random TRISO particle positions within the fuel pebbles, which was injected into the Shift and Serpent models. The 110 Shift and Serpent models were run, and statistical analysis was performed to determine the pebble packing resulting in a k_{eff} closest to the average k_{eff} of all 110 cases. This pebble packing was then injected in the MCNP model. The MCNP model was then used to study the effects of various TRISO particle positioning methods. The TRISO particle positioning is discussed more in Section 3. All models were run with 500 million neutron histories (500 active cycles, 25 inactive cycles, 1 million neutrons per generation), resulting in about a 5 pcm standard deviation for k_{eff} in all calculations.

2.3. Pebble Position Generation Using Chrono::GPU

Random pebble packings were generated using Chrono::GPU, an open-source simulation engine that employs the discrete element method (DEM) to model large granular systems. The DEM approach treats each pebble as a discrete rigid body and simulates particle-particle and particle-wall interactions through contact force models (Hertzian for normal forces, Mindlin for tangential and rolling friction). By numerically integrating Newton's equations of motion, DEM simulations produce realistic random packing configurations that account for gravitational settling, inter-particle friction, and wall effects. Chrono::GPU is optimized for GPU acceleration, enabling efficient simulation of tens of thousands of spherical particles [6]. The HTR-PROTEUS core cavity was represented as a cylindrical container with dimensions matching the benchmark specifications, with graphite reflector walls modeled as fixed boundary surfaces. Fuel and moderator pebbles (6.0 cm diameter) were initially positioned randomly above the cavity with small initial velocities to break symmetry. Contact mechanics parameters representing graphite-graphite interactions (Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, friction coefficients, and coefficient of restitution) were applied. Pebbles were allowed to settle under gravity until reaching mechanical equilibrium, defined by sufficiently small kinetic energy per pebble. The final three-dimensional coordinates of all pebble centers were then extracted for subsequent transport calculations.

2.4. TRISO Particle Modeling in MCNP

Initial attempts to model random TRISO positions in MCNP encountered challenges, as the code does not natively support reading external particle coordinate files in the same format as Shift and Serpent.

Several approaches were evaluated, beginning with ordered lattice representations where TRISO particles were arranged in regular cubic or hexagonal patterns that were computationally efficient but physically unrealistic. To improve upon this, MCNP's URAN card was employed to introduce stochastic variations in the lattice positions, though this still retained underlying lattice structure. Custom Python scripts were then developed to generate 'semi-random' TRISO positions and write them directly into MCNP input files, inspired by the approach set forth in Reference [7]. Eventually, an approach was developed to inject the TRISO coordinates generated by Serpent (i.e., the 'true random' TRISO positions) into the MCNP model, which became the final approach used in this work. This was done to ensure geometric consistency across all three Monte Carlo codes, allowing for direct comparison of code-to-code differences in computed reactivity for identical physical geometries.

The differences in each TRISO positioning method are highlighted in Figure 1. The URAN method is not shown, as transformations using the URAN card are not able to be plotted [5].

Figure 1. TRISO Positioning Methods.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1. Shift and Serpent Results

The question of whether the sample size of 110 is sufficiently large can be answered below in Figure 2, which shows the convergence of the first three moments of k_{eff} (mean, variance, and skewness). If the sample size is not large enough (i.e., a moment does not converge within the set of samples), then the true value of the moment has not yet been reached. As can be seen, the k_{eff} mean and variance both

Figure 2. Serpent k_{eff} Moment Convergence as a Function of Sample Number.

appear to be converged within 110 samples, while the skewness appears to not quite be converged. Using the Shift results to plot the same quantities results in similar behavior. Therefore, the true value of the k_{eff} mean and variance have been determined.

Figure 3 shows a scatterplot of the k_{eff} values as calculated by Serpent, as well as the individual and aggregate standard deviations. As can be seen, the individual standards of deviation are on the order of 5 pcm, while the total uncertainty due to the random pebble positioning is about 30 pcm. Using pebble positions generated by OpenMC results in k_{eff} uncertainties of about 68 pcm; twice that of the Chrono::GPU generated pebble positions. These results are echoed in the Shift results, albeit with variations in the values of k_{eff} .

Figure 3. Individual and Aggregate $k_{eff} \pm 1\sigma$ as Calculated by Serpent.

The variations in k_{eff} are shown more clearly in Figure 4, shows a comparison between the normalized k_{eff} values as calculated by Serpent and Shift.

Figure 4. Scatter-plot of Shift and Serpent Normalized k_{eff} Values as a Function of Sample Number.

As can be seen, there is a slight difference in k_{eff} between the Shift and Serpent models. Testing and validation of the models led to the conclusion that these differences are an artifact of nuclear data differences between Shift and Serpent; Shift uses a customized set of nuclear data, while Serpent directly uses the .ace files from the LANL distribution. There are especially significant differences in available $S(\alpha, \beta)$ thermal scattering data due to differences in the library and particle tracking methods (Woodcock delta versus surface).

Figure 5 shows the difference in the normalized k_{eff} values, and Figure 6 shows the running difference mean of these same values.

Figure 5. Difference Between the Normalized k_{eff} of Shift and Serpent.

As can be seen, the majority of the differences are within one standard deviation, with the average difference being 0. The running mean of the difference between the normalized k_{eff} values converges to 0 as the sample size increases. This indicates that despite the apparent differences, on average, the Shift and Serpent results do indeed agree.

3.2. MCNP TRISO Positioning Results

The results of the TRISO positioning analysis are shown below in Table II. The 'True Random' case refers to the TRISO positions generated by Serpent and then injected into the MCNP model. All Δk_{eff} values are taken with respect to the 'True Random' case.

As can be seen, utilizing realistic, truly random TRISO positioning has a non-negligible effect on k_{eff} ,

Figure 6. Running Mean of the Difference between the Normalized k_{eff} of Shift and Serpent.

Table II. TRISO Positioning Results on k_{eff} With 'True Random' Case Used as the Reference Case.

TRISO Positioning Method	True Random (Ref)	Semi-Random	URAN	Ordered Lattice
k_{eff}	0.997927 ±3.7	0.997772 ±3.9	0.997747 ±3.9	0.997676 ±3.7
Δk_{eff} (pcm)	—	15.5	18.0	25.1

especially when compared to the legacy method of using an ordered lattice. This is to be expected, as using an ordered lattice approach creates artificial, non-physical neutron streaming pathways out of the pebble.

4. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

This work systematically quantified the uncertainty contributions from random pebble packing and TRISO particle positioning in the HTR-PROTEUS Core 4.2 benchmark. Through 110 DEM simulations using Chrono::GPU and Monte Carlo transport calculations with Shift, Serpent, and MCNP, the study established that realistic, random pebble positioning generated using Chrono::GPU contributes approximately 30 pcm of uncertainty to k_{eff} , which is less than half the approximately 68 pcm uncertainty observed with OpenMC-generated packings. This is also about 10 pcm lower than the previous estimate of the pebble packing uncertainty contribution (45 pcm) to the overall 345 pcm variability in k_{eff} . The analysis demonstrated that this sample size was sufficient for convergence of the mean and variance, though higher-order moments require additional sampling.

The comparison of TRISO particle positioning methods revealed that realistic random positioning produces measurably different results compared to simplified geometric approximations. The legacy ordered lattice approach underestimates k_{eff} by approximately 25 pcm relative to true random positioning, likely due to artificial neutron streaming pathways. Semi-random and URAN methods showed smaller but still non-negligible differences of 15.5 and 18.0 pcm, respectively.

Future work will extend this methodology to the remaining HTR-PROTEUS configurations and investigate additional uncertainty sources. The computational framework developed for this work supports the DNCSH project's broader objectives of reducing modeling uncertainties for commercial-scale HALEU fuel.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research made use of Idaho National Laboratory's High Performance Computing systems located at the Collaborative Computing Center and supported by the Office of Nuclear Energy of the U.S. Department of Energy and the Nuclear Science User Facilities under Contract No. DE-AC07-05ID14517.

This material is based upon work supported under a Department of Energy, Office of Nuclear Energy University Nuclear Leadership Program Graduate Fellowship. Any opinions, findings, conclusions, or recommendations expressed in this publication are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the Department of Energy Office of Nuclear Energy.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Shaw. "Participation in and Assessment of the First DNCSH Public Workshop." Technical Report ORNL/TM-2024/3335, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (2024).
- [2] J. Bess and L. Montierth. "Gas Cooled (Thermal) Reactor-GCR,PROTEUS-GCR-EXP-002, CRIT-REAC, HTR-PROTEUS Pebble Bed Experimental Program, Core 4: Random Packing with a 1:1 Moderator-to-Fuel Pebble Ratio." Technical Report NEA/NSC/DOC(2006)1, Idaho National Laboratory (2006).
- [3] T. M. Pandya, S. R. Johnson, T. M. Evans, G. G. Davidson, S. P. Hamilton, and A. T. Godfrey. "Implementation, capabilities, and benchmarking of Shift, a massively parallel Monte Carlo radiation transport code." *Journal of Computational Physics*, **volume 308**, pp. 239–272 (2016). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0021999115008566>.
- [4] Leppänen, Jaakko, Valtavirta, Ville, Rintala, Antti, and Tuominen, Riku. "Status of Serpent Monte Carlo code in 2024." *EPJ Nuclear Sci Technol*, **volume 11**, p. 3 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2024031>.
- [5] J. A. Kulesza, T. R. Adams, J. C. Armstrong, S. R. Bolding, F. B. Brown, J. S. Bull, T. P. Burke, A. R. Clark, R. A. Forster III, J. F. Giron, et al. "MCNP® Code Version 6.3.0 Theory & User Manual." Technical report, Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), Los Alamos, NM (United States) (2022). URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1889957>.
- [6] L. Fang, R. Vanden Heuvel, C. Serban, and N. R. "Chrono::GPU: An Open-Source Simulation Package for Granular Dynamics Using the Discrete Element Method." *Processes*, **volume 9**, p. 1813 (2021). URL <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9101813>.
- [7] B. Impson, M. Elhareef, Z. Wu, and B. Goddard. "Influence of TRISO Fuel Particle Arrangements on Pebble Neutronics and Isotopic Evolution." *Journal of Nuclear Engineering*, **volume 6**, p. 27 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.3390/jne6030027>.